

Investigations on the Kinetics of the Reaction between Potassium Persulphate and Tartaric Acid

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The reaction between potassium persulphate and tartaric acid has been studied from the view point of kinetics. Its order is found to vary from 2 to 1 with the progress of the reaction. A very interesting observation is that the change of order begins during the course of the reaction when the concentration of the persulphate falls to almost half its initial value. The temperature coefficient and the activation energy of the reaction are found to be 1.5 and 8183 cal. respectively. H^+ ion exerts a catalysing influence on the reaction rate. These observations have been explained by a chain mechanism leading to a kinetic expression for the reaction rate.

The reaction between potassium persulphate and several reducing ions, such as oxalate, formate, etc., has been studied by a number of workers and various mechanisms have been suggested to explain the reaction in each case. Ghosh and co-workers following the work of King (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2689; 1928, 50, 2089; 1930, 52, 4779) and Howells (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 462, 466) studied the catalysed and the uncatalysed reactions between oxalic acid and potassium persulphate (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1953, 202, 191; 1956, 205, 332). Allen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 3599) studied the copper-catalysed reaction between oxalate and persulphate ions. The kinetics of the reaction between potassium formate and potassium persulphate also formed a topic of study by Ghosh *et al.* (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1953, 202, 199; 1957, 207, 161). The authors studied the uncatalysed reaction between oxalic acid and potassium persulphate and observed it to be extremely slow with regard to the reduction of the persulphate by the acid (*Agra Univ. Jour. Res., Sci.* 1957, 6, 2). A tentative mechanism for this reaction covering its various features has been suggested (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1959, 211, 161; 1960, 214, 179).

A search of the literature shows that the kinetics of the reaction between potassium persulphate and tartaric acid has not been studied so far. The reaction appeared interesting to the authors, particularly because of the presence of reducing hydroxyl group in the tartaric acid molecule. The present communication deals with the kinetics of the reduction of potassium persulphate by tartaric acid with a view to arriving at a probable mechanism of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of potassium persulphate and tartaric acid (both Analar quality, B.D.H) were prepared in double distilled water. Required amounts of freshly prepared solutions were adjusted to desired temperatures before these were mixed in pyrex conical flasks kept in a thermostat maintained at those temperatures. After suitable intervals of time 10 c.c. aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn and analysed for residual potassium persulphate by the method mentioned in our previous publications (*loc. cit.*).

The unimolecular and bimolecular velocity coefficients were calculated by the usual formulas:

$$k_1 = (2.303/t) \log a/(a-x)$$
$$k_2 = x/at(a-x)$$

Influence of Temperature on Reaction Velocity:

TABLE I

<i>t.</i>	(<i>a-x</i>).	$k_1 \times 10^3$.	$k_2 \times 10^3$.	(<i>a-x</i>).	$k_1 \times 10^3$,	$k_2 \times 10^3$.	(<i>a-x</i>)	$k_1 \times 10^3$	$k_2 \times 10^3$
	(<i>a</i>) Temp. = 50°.			(<i>b</i>) Temp. = 40°.			(<i>c</i>) Temp. = 30°.		
0 mins.	9.9 c.c.	..	-	10.0 c.c.	-	-	9.9 c.c.	-	-
30	7.8	7.945	0.9065	8.0	5.028	0.5426	-	-	-
60	6.5	7.011	0.8806	7.0	4.574	0.5262	8.5	2.541	0.2773
90	5.6	6.331	0.8620	6.8	4.286	0.5229	-	-	-
120	4.8	6.034	0.8945	6.1	4.120	0.5328	7.5	2.313	0.2694
150	4.1	5.878	0.9526	5.5	3.981	0.5454	-	-	-
180	3.6	5.620	0.9819	5.0	3.851	0.5555	6.8	2.086	0.2559
210	3.1	5.608	1.090	4.5	3.804	0.5821	-	-	-
240	2.6	5.571	mean 1.181	4.1	3.715	mean 0.5996	6.2	1.950	0.2512
270	2.2	5.571	=5.862 1.309	-	-	=3.747	-	-	-
300	1.9	5.503	1.418	3.4	3.596	0.6471	5.6	1.900	0.2386
330	1.6	5.525	1.588	-	-	-	-	-	-
360	1.3	5.640	1.857	2.8	3.536	0.7142	5.2	1.798	0.2536
390	1.1	5.633	2.072	-	-	-	4.8	1.724	0.2557
420	0.9	5.699	2.405	-	-	-	5.6	1.800	0.2559
480	..	..	..	-	-	-	4.4	1.690	0.2631
540	..	..	..	-	-	-	4.0	1.678	0.2759

A scrutiny of the values of k_1 and k_2 in Table I shows that at 50°, at equal concentrations of the reactants, the reaction follows the second order equation up to 120 mins. and then first order till completion. As the temperature is lowered, the period of second order increases, viz., 180 mins. at 40° and 420 mins. at 30°; in each case the second order is followed by the first order reaction. It is further observed that the change from the second order to the first takes place when the concentration of the persulphate falls to about half of its initial value. The temperature coefficient of the reaction between 40°/50°, as calculated from the mean unimolecular coefficients (in parenthesis) comes out to be 1.5 and the corresponding activation energy comes out to be 8183 cal.

Order of the Reaction

By same Fractional Reaction Period.— Fig. 1 gives the $x-t$ curves for the reaction at 50° for two different concentrations of the reactants. For curve 1 the concentration of each of the reactants was 0.02 M (C_1), whereas in

 FIG 1. Order by $\frac{1}{2}$ time period.

curve 2, the concentration of persulphate was $0.02M$ and that of tartaric acid $0.04M (C_2)$. The order (n) of the reaction, calculated by the expression given below, is shown in Table II.

$$n = 1 + \frac{\log t_1 - \log t_2}{\log C_2 - \log C_1}$$

where, t_1 and t_2 are the times for the same fraction of the reaction at concentrations C_1 and C_2 .

TABLE II
Temp. = 50° .

No.	Fraction of reaction.	Times (mins.) from Fig. 1.		C_2/C_1	n .
		t_1 .	t_2 .		
1	1/4	39	24	2.0	1.75
2	1/2	114	90	2.0	1.34
3	3/4	255	204	2.0	1.32

Data in Table II show that the reaction first follows second order till 1/4 of the reaction is completed. After this it proceeds first order.

By Isolation Method.—The velocity of reaction between persulphate and tartaric acid may be represented by the equation:

$$-\frac{dC_{S_2O_8^{2-}}}{dt} = k C_1^m C_2^n$$

where, C_1 and C_2 are the concentrations of the persulphate and tartaric acid respectively, and $m+n$ represents the total order of the reaction. For determining m and n , two sets of experiments were performed in which the concentrations of tartaric acid (C_2' & C_2'') were varied but kept in large excess of persulphate, the concentration of which was kept constant. The unimolecular velocity constants (k_1' & k_1'') were calculated for both the experiments, which gave the value of ' m '. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III
Temp = 50° .

t .	$(K_2S_2O_8)_0 = 0.005M (C_1)$. $(Tar Ac)_0 = 0.05M (C_2')$.		$(K_2S_2O_8)_0 = 0.005M (C_1)$. $(Tar Ac)_0 = 0.10M (C_2'')$.	
	$(a-x)$.	k_1' .	$(a-x)$.	k_1'' .
0 min.	9.8 c.c.	..	9.9 c.c.	..
15	6.2	0.0305	5.8	0.0358
30	3.8	0.0316	2.7	0.0433
45	2.2	0.0332	1.5	0.0422
60	1.2	0.0335	0.25	0.0588

The value of n was calculated by the expression:

$$n = \log \frac{k_1'}{k_1''} / \log \frac{C_2''}{C_2'}$$

Its value comes out to be 0.33, thus, the total order of the reaction by this method is 1.3.

Effect of Concentration of the Reactants on Reaction Velocity

Tartaric Acid.—The constancy of the unimolecular coefficients is noticeable after the concentration of the persulphate is reduced to almost half its initial value. It is to be noted that the period of unimolecular reaction tends to increase with the increase in the concentration of tartaric acid.

TABLE IV
 $[(K_2S_2O_8)]_0 = 0.02M$. Temp. = 50° .

t.	Concentration of tartaric acid.				
	0.0025 M.	0.005 M.	0.01 M. ($k_1 \times 10^3$)	0.02 M.	0.04 M.
0 min.	..	..	..	..	..
30	3.585	4.353	7.186	7.945	11.080
60	3.174	4.237	6.339	7.011	8.913
120	2.686	3.550	5.281	6.034	7.147
180	2.455	3.311	4.977	5.620	6.823
240	2.258	3.152	4.798	5.571	7.344
300	2.113	2.986	4.690	5.503	7.980
360	2.101	2.862	4.708	5.640	7.783

Potassium Persulphate.—The unimolecular coefficients show constancy when the concentration of the persulphate lies between 0.001M and 0.002M. Beyond 0.002M, viz., at 0.016M and 0.032M the unimolecular coefficients do not become constant until the concentration of persulphate is reduced to about 50% of its initial value. Another interesting feature of the reaction is that on increasing the concentration of the persulphate the values of k_1 decrease (Table V).

TABLE V
 $[(CHOH.COOH)_2]_0 = 0.02M$. Temp. = 50° .

t.	Concentrations of potassium persulphate.					
	0.001 M.	0.002 M.	0.004 M. ($k_1 \times 10^3$)	0.008 M.	0.016 M.	0.032 M.
0 mins.	..	..	..	..	..	..
30	29.32	27.20	17.68	15.81	11.21	12.26
60	33.75	28.60	19.84	15.79	10.81	7.58
90	..	30.00	22.03	15.63	10.10	6.88
120	..	..	23.60	16.22	9.72	6.22
150	..	..	..	16.70	9.70	5.94
180	..	..	..	17.77	9.47	5.79
210	..	..	..	..	9.27	5.80
240	..	..	..	..	9.44	5.77
270	..	..	..	..	..	5.75
300	..	..	..	..	..	5.72
330	..	..	..	..	..	5.70

Comparative Study of the Effect of Sulphuric Acid, Sodium Acetate and Oxygen on Reaction Velocity

It is observed from Table VI that oxygen and sulphuric acid accelerate the reaction, whereas sodium acetate suppresses it, but in each case the reaction is of first order. It is further noted that in presence of sodium acetate the reaction has a period of induction, as high as about six hours at a concentration of 1.0N. Some observations showed that the reaction is slightly catalysed by the glass surface.

TABLE VI
 $(K_2S_2O_8)_0 = [(CHOH.COOH)_2]_0 = 0.02M$. Temp. = 50° .

<i>t</i> , 0 mins.	Nil.	Oxygen at const. pressure ($k_1 \times 10^3$).	0.05N- H_2SO_4 .	0.05N- CH_3COONa .
30	7.945	8.474	13.36	0.0
60	7.011	7.003	12.89	3.11
90	6.331	..	12.67	3.81
120	6.034	7.063	12.63	3.85
150	5.878	..	12.65	3.63
180	5.620	6.960	12.79	3.42
210	5.608	..	13.40	3.30
240	5.571	6.836	..	3.06

DISCUSSION

The reaction between potassium persulphate and tartaric acid may be represented by the following stoichiometric equation:

which suggests that the reaction should be of the sixth order (concentration of water being regarded as constant). But the experimental results show that its order changes from two to one, the period of transition being dependent on temperature, concentrations of the reactants, *pH* of the reaction mixture, etc. These observations can be explained by the following chain mechanism similar to that suggested by the authors for the decomposition of persulphate in aqueous solution (*loc. cit.*).

In view of the above mechanism, we have:

$$-\frac{dC_{S_2O_8^{2-}}}{dt} = k_1 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} + k_6 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} - C_{CO_2^-} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

By employing the usual stationary state approximations for the radicals CO_2^- , SO_4^- and Tar^- (tartrate radical) and assuming step (7) to be negligibly slow at low concentrations of CO_2^- and SO_4^- radicals, we get

$$C_{CO_2^-} = \frac{k_4 C_{SO_4^-} C_{Tar^-}}{k_6 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}}} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

and

$$C_{SO_4^-} = \frac{k_1 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}}}{k_2 C_{H_2O}} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

Substituting these values in expression (i) we obtain

$$-\frac{dC_{S_2O_8^{2-}}}{dt} = k_1 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} + \frac{k_6 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} k_4 C_{SO_4} C_{Tar^{2-}}}{k_8 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}}} \quad \dots \dots \dots (iv)$$

$$= k_1 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} + \frac{k_4 k_6 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} C_{Tar^{2-}}}{k_8 C_{H_2O}} \quad \dots \dots \dots (v)$$

In a dilute solution C_{H_2O} may be regarded as constant; hence,

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{dC_{S_2O_8^{2-}}}{dt} &= k_1 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} + (k_4 k_6 / k_8') C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} C_{Tar^{2-}} \quad (\text{where } k_8' = k_8 C_{H_2O}) \\ &= k_1 C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} [1 + (k_4 C_{Tar^{2-}} / k_8')] \quad \dots \dots \dots (vi) \end{aligned}$$

At lower temperatures, e.g., at 30°, step (2) is negligibly slow (*loc. cit.*) so that k_8' is very small compared to k_4 , hence $[1 + (k_4 C_{Tar^{2-}} / k_8')]$ becomes almost equal to $(k_4 C_{Tar^{2-}} / k_8')$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i.e., } -\frac{dC_{S_2O_8^{2-}}}{dt} &= (k_1 k_4 / k_8') C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} C_{Tar^{2-}} \\ &= k C_{S_2O_8^{2-}} C_{Tar^{2-}} \end{aligned}$$

This equation is supported by Table I (c) and by I (a) and I (b) during the beginning of the reaction. The change of order from 2 to 1 (Table I) after certain interval of time at 40° and 50° is due to the fall of concentration of persulphate to such a low value, as a result of the initial bimolecular reaction, that the concentration of tartaric acid becomes very large compared to that of the persulphate and the reaction becomes pseudounimolecular. It is interesting to note that this change of order from 2 to 1 takes place when the concentration of persulphate is reduced almost to half of its initial value. These observations are supported by the data recorded in Tables IV and V.

The catalysing influence of oxygen (Table VI) supports step (5) of the suggested mechanism. H^+ ions also appear to catalyse the reactions, as shown (Table VI) by the increase of reaction rate in presence of sulphuric acid, and decrease of reaction rate in presence of sodium acetate. The effect of perchloric, hydrochloric and nitric acids is similar to that of sulphuric acid.

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